

Inhibition of corrosion of copper by polyvinylpyrrolidone-iodine in sulfuric acid medium

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ABSTRACT

The use of polymers as corrosion inhibitors has attracted considerable attention due to their low prices, inherent stability, availability and cost effectiveness. Corrosion inhibition by such compounds is usually attributed to their adsorption at the metal-solution interface. In this study, the effect of polyvinylpyrrolidone-iodine on the corrosion behavior of copper in sulfuric acid solution was investigated using the weight loss method and scanning electron microscopy (SEM). The effect of inhibitor concentration, solution temperature and immersion time on the corrosion of copper was investigated. The effect of temperature on the inhibition mechanism of inhibitor on copper surface was studied at different temperatures (293-323 K), and the inhibition efficiency (IE) increased with increasing temperatures. The maximum IE of 90.22% was obtained at a temperature of 50 °C, a concentration of polyvinylpyrrolidone-iodine inhibitor of 150 mg L⁻¹ and a H₂SO₄ acid concentration of 0.5 M. The kinetic and thermodynamic parameters for the corrosion of copper and the adsorption of the inhibitor were determined and discussed. The most remarkable inhibition efficiency was confirmed by the presence of the film formed on the metal surface by scanning electron microscopy (SEM).

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1. Introduction

Copper and its alloys are widely used in industry due to some advantageous properties such as high electrical and thermal conductivity, good mechanical workability and formability, and good corrosion resistance [1]. In addition, copper is also used for coating roofs and sculptures. Some of these components or machine tools are not protected when exposed to adverse environments during operation. Acid cleaning is regularly performed to clean and descale these systems. These adverse effects can be minimized or eliminated by using various techniques to protect the metal surface from aggressive environments. Corrosion inhibition is of great practical importance as it is often used to reduce or prevent wastage of engineering materials and to minimize the cost of corrosion protection [2, 3]. A corrosion inhibitor is a chemical compound that can reduce the effects of a corrosive medium by decreasing its rate of attack [4]. These inhibitors can be inorganic or organic compounds [5-8]. Researchers are working to find a good corrosion inhibitor which has many properties such as high solubility, non-toxicity, biodegradability, stability, short- and long-term durability and low cost [9]. Polyvinylpyrrolidone added to iodine

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forms a complex called povidone-iodine, which is used for its antiseptic properties in various products such as liquid soaps, ointments, surgical scrubs and pessaries, or as an antibacterial and antimicrobial agent in medical devices [10, 11]. The present work reports the anticorrosive behavior of polyvinylpyrrolidone-iodine on copper in sulfuric acid medium. The effects of concentration, temperature, and immersion time on inhibitor performance were studied. The thermodynamic activation parameters for both the dissolution and adsorption processes are calculated and discussed. The inhibition effect was studied by weight loss method. Further SEM analysis was carried out to reveal the surface coverage.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Specimen preparation

Copper specimens were used in the weight loss experiments. Prior to tests, the copper material was abraded using a series of emery paper sheets (from 600 to 1200 grains) to be finally washed with water and acetone (99%, Sigma-Aldrich, Germany). The solution of 0.5 M sulfuric acid was prepared by dilution of H₂SO₄ (98%, Merck, Germany) with distilled water.

2.2. Weight loss measurements

The weight loss method for monitoring corrosion rate is useful because of its ease of use and reliability. Sample measurements of copper were calculated in the sulfuric acid solution with and without the addition of various concentrations of polyvinylpyrrolidone iodine. All experiments were carried out in triplicate and the data presented are mean values of the results obtained.

The corrosion rate ‘CR’ and the inhibitor efficiency were calculated via the following equations (Eqs.1, 2) [12]:

$$CR = \frac{w}{S \times t} \quad (1)$$

where w denotes the weight loss (mg), S represents the sample area (cm⁻²) and t symbolizes the immersion time (h⁻¹). The corrosion inhibition efficiency (IE %) and the surface coverage (θ) were calculated from the CR values:

$$IE (\%) = \frac{CR - CR_{inh}}{CR} \times 100 \quad (2)$$

where CR and CR_{inh} denote the obtained corrosion rates in the absence and presence of the inhibitor.

3. Results and discussions

3.1. Effect of Concentration and Temperature on Inhibition Efficiency

Temperature can alter the interactions between the copper and the sulfuric acid in the absence and presence of various concentrations of the polyvinylpyrrolidone iodine during a two-hour immersion period. The effect of the concentration of the inhibitor on the corrosion of copper in 0.5 M H₂SO₄ is shown in Fig.1. It was observed that the inhibition efficiency (IE) of polyvinylpyrrolidone iodine increases with an increase in the concentration of inhibitor and temperature [13]. With the increase in temperature, the amount of adsorbed molecules on the surface also increases, so that the equilibrium shifts to more adsorption and less desorption. The increase in IE is due to the blocking effect on the surface of the metal by adsorption, film formation mechanism and also due to the presence of protonated nitrogen, the oxygen and the iodide atoms of polyvinylpyrrolidone iodine [14]. The maximum efficiency of 83.67-90.22% was obtained at concentrations of 100-150 mg L⁻¹ of the inhibitor and at 333 K. This inhibitory power is more remarkable at concentration of 150 mg L⁻¹.

Fig. 1. Variation in the inhibition efficiency against concentration of inhibitor in 0.5 M H₂SO₄ solution at different temperatures.

3.2. Effect of immersion time on inhibition efficiency

The immersion time is another important parameter which establishes the inhibitory effect on the metallic surfaces. The results presented in Table 2 show the effect of immersion time on the inhibition effect and corrosion rate of copper immersed in 0.5 M H₂SO₄ solution at 323 K in the absence and presence of polyvinylpyrrolidone iodine at different time intervals up to 96 hours. Table 2 shows that the inhibitory effect increases by 52.91–90.22% with the immersion time of 1 to 2 hours. Thereafter, it remains almost stable (higher than 95%) due to the stability of adsorbed layer on copper surface from 3 to 96 hours. It was found that with increasing immersion time, the corrosion rates of inhibitor decrease, which shows the good behavior of polyvinylpyrrolidone-iodine on copper surface with increasing immersion time.

Table 2. Corrosion rate and inhibition efficiency for copper in 0.5 M H₂SO₄ in the absence and presence of polyvinylpyrrolidone-iodine at 323 K.

Time (h)	CR _{corr} (mg h ⁻¹ cm ⁻²)	CR _{inh} (mg h ⁻¹ cm ⁻²)	IE (%)
1	0.90335	0.42538	52.91
2	0.12708	0.01242	90.22
3	0.15325	0.00677	95.58
24	0.32167	0.01097	96.59
48	0.21671	0.00756	96.51
72	0.22336	0.00819	96.33
96	0.12571	0.00464	96.31

3.3. Activation parameters of the corrosion process

To evaluate the adsorption of inhibitor, the corrosion rates calculated at different temperatures (293–323 K) in the absence and presence of polyvinylpyrrolidone-iodine were used to calculate the activation energy, activation enthalpy, and activation entropy of the metal dissolution. Arrhenius equation can be used with success to show the effect of temperature on the inhibitory action of the inhibitor under study. It is represented by the following equation [4]:

$$CR = A \times \exp\left(-\frac{E_a}{RT}\right) \quad (3)$$

where CR is the corrosion rate ($\text{mg h}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-2}$), A is the Arrhenius pre-exponential factor, E_a (kJ mol^{-1}) is the activation energy, R is the gas constant ($8.314 \text{ J mol}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$) and T is the temperature (K).

The values of E_a for copper in sulfuric acid without and with various concentrations of inhibitors were determined from the slope of the $\ln(\text{CR})$ plot versus $1/T$. The values activation enthalpy ΔH_a and activation entropy ΔS_a can be calculated by the slope ($-\Delta H_a/R$) and intercept $[(\Delta S_a/R) + (\ln(R/Nh))]$ of the above plot $\ln(\text{CR}/T)$ versus $1/T$. Using the following transition state equation (4) [15], the values of E_a , ΔH_a and ΔS_a can be calculated as show in Table 3.

$$\ln\left(\frac{CR}{T}\right) = \left[\frac{\Delta S_a}{R} + \ln\left(\frac{R}{Nh}\right)\right] - \left(\frac{\Delta H_a}{RT}\right) \quad (4)$$

where h is Planks constant, N is Avogadro's number, ΔS_a is the entropy of activation, and ΔH_a is the enthalpy of activation.

As the temperature increases, the adsorption of the polyvinylpyrrolidone-iodine molecule on the copper surface increases significantly, resulting in a decrease in the activation energy. The positive values of ΔH_a in the absence of the inhibitor indicate the endothermic nature of the copper dissolution process [16].

The average value of the difference between activation energy and enthalpy change ($E_a - \Delta H_a$) was 2.55 kJ mol^{-1} for all concentrations, which was the exact value of the product of the gas constant and the average temperature of the experiment (293-323 K). This result indicates that the corrosion process is a unimolecular reaction with the evolution of hydrogen gas [17]. The activation entropy increased more negatively with increasing inhibitor concentration. The negative value of ΔS_a indicates that there is a decrease in disorder during the transition from the reactants to the reaction complex [11].

Table 3. Activation parameters of polyvinylpyrrolidone-iodine on copper in a 0.5 M H_2SO_4 solution

C (mg L^{-1})	R ²	E _a (kJ mol^{-1})	R ²	ΔH _a (kJ mol^{-1})	ΔS _a ($\text{J mol}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$)
0	0.998	11.26	0.998	8.71	-293.24
10	0.982	-10.14	0.987	-12.69	-366.61
50	0.993	-14.06	0.995	-16.61	-382.21
100	0.998	-20.2	0.998	-22.75	-405.75
150	0.991	-26.10	0.992	-28.65	-428.09

3.4. Adsorption Isotherm

Adsorption isotherms furnish information on the interaction between the inhibitor molecules and the metal surface. Corrosion inhibition of copper in the presence of polyvinylpyrrolidone-iodine has been investigated to the adsorption on the metal surface, and this was generally confirmed from the fit of the experimental data to different adsorption isotherms.

The plots of C/θ versus C yield a straight line with approximately unit slope, indicating that the inhibitor under study follows the Langmuir adsorption isotherm (Figure 3).

Fig. 2. Langmuir isotherm for the adsorption of polyvinylpyrrolidone-iodine on copper in sulfuric acid.

The K_{ads} values can be calculated from the intercept lines on the C/θ -axis. According to this isotherm, θ is related to C by this equation (5) [18]:

$$\frac{C}{\theta} = \frac{1}{K_{ads}} + C \tag{5}$$

Where, θ is the surface coverage by inhibitor molecule, C is the concentration, and K_{ads} is the equilibrium constant ($L g^{-1}$) for the adsorption-desorption process.

The free energy (ΔG_{ads}) of the adsorption of inhibitor on copper surface can be evaluated with the following equation (6) [19]:

$$\Delta G_{ads} = -RT \ln(1000 \times K_{ads}) \tag{6}$$

where R is the gas constant ($J mol^{-1} K^{-1}$) and T is the absolute temperature (K).

The adsorption enthalpy (ΔH_{ads}) can be calculated by the intercept of the above plot ΔG_{ads} against T (Figure 3), using the following transition state equation (7) [20]:

$$\Delta G_{ads} = \Delta H_{ads} - T\Delta S_{ads} \tag{7}$$

Figure 3 shows that there is a linear relationship between ΔG_{ads} and T . The adsorption enthalpy (ΔH_{ads}) and the adsorption entropy calculated using equation (7) and listed in Table 4.

The adsorption equilibrium constant increases with the increase in temperature. This shows that temperature favours adsorption rather than desorption of the inhibitor on the copper surface. An exothermic adsorption process can mean either chemisorption or physisorption or a mixture of both processes. The endothermic adsorption process is clearly assigned to chemisorption [3].

Fig. 3. Free energy versus temperature for adsorption polyvinylpyrrolidone-iodine on copper surface.

The more water molecules are desorbed from the metal surface by the adsorption of an inhibitor molecule, the higher the entropy value [21]. The chemisorption of the inhibitor on the copper surface can also be deduced from the value of ΔG_{ads} . Normally, a value of ΔG_{ads} around -20 kJ mol^{-1} indicates that physisorption is the most important process due to the attraction of the Vander walls between the copper and the inhibitor, but when the value of ΔG_{ads} becomes -30 kJ mol^{-1} or even more negative, chemisorption would dominate [21].

Table 4. Thermodynamic parameters for the adsorption polyvinylpyrrolidone-iodine on copper in a 0.5 M H_2SO_4 solution at different temperatures

T (K)	R^2	$K_{\text{ads}} (\text{L g}^{-1})$	$\Delta H_{\text{ads}} (\text{kJ mol}^{-1})$	$\Delta S_{\text{ads}} (\text{J mol}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1})$	$\Delta G_{\text{ads}} (\text{kJ mol}^{-1})$
293	0.991	5.86		305.18	-21.13
303	0.978	28.51	68.29	310.66	-25.84
313	0.985	55.12		308.94	-28.41
323	0.991	86.61		305.94	-30.53

The negative free energy values for the inhibitor range from -21.13 to $-30.53 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$. These negative signs indicate the stability of the adsorbed layer on the copper surface and the spontaneity of the adsorption process, while positive signs symbolise a non-spontaneous adsorption process. This free energy result indicates that the adsorption of polyvinylpyrrolidone-iodine on the copper surface occurs in a possible mixture (physisorption and chemisorption), with chemisorption being the more dominant adsorption mechanism.

3.5 Scanning electron microscope

The inhibitory effect of polyvinylpyrrolidone-iodine on the corrosion reaction was investigated using the scanning electron microscopic (SEM) images of the corroded copper surface in the absence and presence of the inhibitor (Fig. 4). It can be seen that the metal surface corrodes uniformly in the acidic solution (without inhibitor) (Fig. 4b). This clearly shows that in the absence of the inhibitor, the copper has deteriorated to a great extent, in contrast

to the copper surface (Fig. 4a), which appears smooth with only a few lines resulting from polishing. These microscopic images show that the smoothness of the tested metal in the presence of the inhibitor (Fig. 4c) has remarkably improved compared to the blank. The smoothness of the surface is caused by the adsorption of the inhibitor molecules on the metal surface, which shields the surface from the aggressive solution.

Fig. 4. SEM images of copper specimens corroded in 0.5 M sulfuric acid solution: (a) before immersion (polished), (b) the absence and (c) presence of polyvinylpyrrolidone-iodine.

4. Conclusion

The polyvinylpyrrolidone iodine inhibitor showed good inhibition efficiency against copper metal corrosion in an acidic sulfuric acid solution. The inhibition efficiency was found to increase with increasing concentration of inhibitor and temperature. The negative values of adsorption free energy indicate the spontaneous adsorption of inhibitor on copper surface. The value of ΔG_{ads} becomes more negative, indicating that chemisorption dominates at high temperatures. The thermodynamic parameters show that the adsorption of polyvinylpyrrolidone-iodine on the copper surface obeys the Langmuir adsorption isotherm. The SEM studies showed that the copper surface with the inhibitor molecule appeared smoother and more uniform and exhibited less roughness than the surface in the uninhibited solution.

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